

The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance Mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) on ASN Employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office

Haryu Darmaeti¹, Yuni Siswanti², Sri Dwi Ari Ambarwati³

^{1,2,3} Master's Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, Veteran National Development University Yogyakarta

ABSTRACT: The Regional Secretariat is a key element in fostering a more professional and change-adaptive bureaucracy. According to the 2024 Performance Report of the Gunungkidul Regency Regional Secretariat, several strategic indicators have not yet been fully achieved. This reflects a performance gap between expectations and actual ASN performance. This study aims to analyze the influence of transformational leadership and employee engagement on employee performance mediated by organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office. This study used a sample of 112 civil servants at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat office. The research method employed descriptive analysis to observe the characteristics of respondents and the research variables. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The study found that transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) did not significantly influence employee performance, while employee engagement significantly influenced employee performance. Furthermore, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) mediated the relationship between transformational leadership and employee engagement on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Employee engagement, Employees performance, Organizational citizenship behavior, Transformational leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Amidst demands for increasingly accountable, responsive, and results-oriented governance, improving the performance of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) has become a key focus of bureaucratic reform. As part of its commitment to achieving good governance, the Gunungkidul Regency Government emphasized in its 2025 Regional Government Work Plan (RKPD) that improving the quality of bureaucracy and public services is one of the main strategic objectives for transforming regional development and achieving development goals. According to the 2024 Performance Report of the Gunungkidul Regency Regional Secretariat, several strategic indicators have not been fully achieved. Although the performance accountability score for Gunungkidul Regency government agencies (AKIP) in 2024 reached 82.66, falling within the "satisfactory" category, this achievement still falls below the highest category, "very satisfactory" (minimum score of 90) (Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform, 2024). This reflects the existence of a performance gap between the expectations and reality of ASN performance. On the other hand, employee performance is a crucial factor in determining the success of implementing government programs, especially in a dynamic and complex public bureaucratic environment.

In an effort to answer these challenges, transformational leadership is a relevant approach to be implemented in response to bureaucratic complexity, the dynamics of regulatory changes, and increasing public demands for quality public services. Transformational leadership is a leadership style that is able to inspire, motivate, and empower employees to exceed expectations, through the formation of a shared vision, intellectual stimulation, and individual attention (Avolio & Bass, 1994). Leaders with a transformational style not only emphasize achieving employee work targets, but also build a work environment that is conducive to positive change, encourage innovation, and foster long-term commitment to the organization.

Besides leadership factors, employee engagement is a crucial aspect in driving work productivity. Employee engagement reflects the extent to which employees feel emotionally, cognitively, and behaviorally involved in their work and the organization. Schaufeli & Bakker, (2016) stated that Employee Engagement is the involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm of individuals towards the work they do, which reflects the extent to which employees feel motivated, committed, and have an emotional connection with the organization. In a bureaucratic environment that tends to be hierarchical, the existence of engagement is

important because employees who feel engaged tend to be more proactive, loyal, and solution-oriented, which ultimately has an impact on better performance.

In the context of a local government bureaucracy such as the Gunungkidul Regency Secretariat, which is characterized by a hierarchical and formal organizational structure, the influence of leadership and employee engagement on performance needs to be understood more contextually. OCB is thought to play a crucial role as a psychological and behavioral mechanism that bridges the influence of these two variables on performance. Organ, (1995) stated that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is voluntary behavior demonstrated by employees in helping coworkers and supporting a positive work environment without any formal demands from the company. Employees who have high OCB tend to show caring attitudes, cooperate, and take the initiative to help coworkers or improve team efficiency.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of transformational leadership and employee engagement on employee performance, mediated by organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), among civil servants at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office. The results of this study are expected to confirm previous research and provide input for decision-making among civil servants at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.

RESEARCH JOB

This study aims to determine the influence of Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behavior on ASN employees at the Gunung Kidul Regional Secretariat Office. Specifically, this study aims to:

1. Analyze the influence of transformational leadership on the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
2. Analyze the influence of employee engagement on the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
3. Analyze the influence of transformational leadership on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
4. Analyze the influence of employee engagement on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
5. Analyze the influence of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) on the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
6. Testing the role of OCB as a mediating variable in the relationship between transformational leadership and the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
7. Testing the role of OCB as a mediating variable in the relationship between employee engagement and ASN employee performance at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

According to Robbins, (2003), transformational leadership is a leader who is able to inspire his employees to prioritize the progress of the organization over personal interests, provide good attention to employees and is able to change the awareness of his employees in seeing old problems in new ways. A transformational leader also has an important role in encouraging and supporting his subordinates by providing encouragement, recognition, and trust that builds the active involvement of each individual in the organization. Avolio et al., (1999) stated that transformational leadership is an individual's ability to instill inspiration in employees, accommodate their interests and in such a way can have a strong, fundamental influence on the hearts of other employees.

Employee Engagement

Schaufeli & Bakker, (2016) stated that Employee Engagement is the involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm of individuals towards the work they do, which reflects the extent to which employees feel motivated, committed, and have an emotional connection with the organization. Employees with high levels of engagement tend to demonstrate greater dedication, work with enthusiasm, and have a sense of responsibility toward their tasks and company goals. Atthohiri & Wijayati, (2021) state that Employee Engagement is a form of employee direct contribution to their work, reflected in enthusiasm, dedication, and a strong appreciation for their duties and responsibilities.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organ, (1995) defines Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as voluntary behavior demonstrated by employees in helping coworkers and supporting a positive work environment without formal demands from the company. OCB reflects individual contributions that go beyond the duties and responsibilities stipulated in their job descriptions. Wiguna et al., (2022) state that employees with high OCB tend to demonstrate caring attitudes, cooperate, and take the initiative to help coworkers or improve team efficiency.

Employee Performance

Kementerian PANRB RI, (2022) states that employee performance is the result or level of success of a person in carrying out their duties and responsibilities during a certain period, which is evaluated based on various indicators, such as work standards, targets, objectives, or criteria that have been previously determined and agreed upon. A good level of performance indicates that an individual is not only able to meet expectations but also strives to improve skills, adapt to change, and make a greater contribution to the team or organization. Performance reflects the extent to which a person is able to carry out their work effectively and efficiently, both in terms of productivity, quality of work results, and their contribution to organizational goals Ridwan et al., (2020).

INTER-VARIABLE INFLUENCE

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance

Research conducted by Ramadhani & Indawati, (2021) found that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on employee performance. A transformational leader plays a crucial role in encouraging and supporting subordinates through encouragement, recognition, and trust, which fosters active engagement within the organization. Research conducted by Saputro, (2021) also found that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on employee performance. Similarly, research by Muhammad et al., (2023) found that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on employee performance.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on Employee Performance

Research conducted by Awalia & Yanuar (2024) shows that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on employee performance. When employees are highly engaged, they tend to work with dedication, contribute maximally, and demonstrate loyalty to the company. Kurniawati & Raharja (2023) found in their research that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on employee performance. Similarly, research conducted by Supriyanto et al., (2021) shows that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on employee performance.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on OCB

Research conducted by Nemr & liu, (2021) shows that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on OCB. A leader who is able to accommodate employee interests and influence individual employees has the potential to foster OCB attitudes in employees. In their research, Zalianty & Rojuaniah, (2023) found that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on OCB. A similar finding was also noted by Kadek et al., (2024), who showed that transformational leadership has a significant positive influence on OCB.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on OCB

Research conducted by Alshaabani et al., (2021) shows that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on OCB. When employees feel emotionally and professionally engaged, they not only focus on their primary work but also show concern for the work environment. Research conducted by Mahmudi & Farida Elmi, (2020) also shows that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on OCB. Similarly, research by Shams et al., (2020) shows that employee engagement has a significant positive influence on OCB.

The Influence of OCB on Employee Performance

Research conducted by Sugiharjo (2020) shows that OCB has a significant positive influence on employee performance. Employees with high OCB tend to demonstrate caring, cooperation, and initiative, which not only strengthen interpersonal relationships but also enhance teamwork dynamics. In her research, Istanti (2021) found that OCB has a significant positive effect on employee performance. Similarly, research by Ridwan (2020) found that OCB has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

FRAMEWORK

Hypothesis

- H1 : sformational Leadership influences the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H2 : Employee Engagement influences the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H3 : Transformational Leadership influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H4 : Employee Engagement influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H5 : Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) influences the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H6 : Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) mediates the relationship between Transformational Leadership and the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.
- H7 : Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) mediates the relationship between Employee Engagement and the performance of ASN employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office.

RESEARCH METHOD

Data Type and Sources

The data used in this study includes primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained directly from respondents through questionnaires distributed to 112 civil servants at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office. Secondary data were obtained from various relevant sources to support and enrich the research analysis. Secondary data sources included publications from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), local government reports, scientific journal articles, academic documents, and other literature related to the development of the Regional Secretariat Office.

Population and Sample

The population in this study was all employees at the Gunungkidul Regency Regional Secretariat Office, including civil servants (PNS), civil servant candidates (CPNS), and government employee candidates (PPPK), totaling 121. This study used a

census technique, a data collection method in which the entire population is used as research subjects due to its relatively small population size, with no exceptions. This means that all members of the population are examined individually to obtain complete and accurate data.

Analisis Techniques

This study employed descriptive analysis to observe the characteristics of respondents and research variables. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach. This technique was chosen for its ability to handle complex research models, including second-order reflective-formative models, and to evaluate and interpret causal relationships between latent constructs. To estimate higher-order constructs, a two-step PLS approach was used, in which the first stage involves testing the dimensional constructs (first-order) separately to obtain latent variable scores. In the second stage, these latent scores are used as indicators to measure the second-order constructs as a whole (Hair et al., 2014).

Operational Definiton

Variable	Operaitonal Definiton	Indikator
Transformational Leadership (X1)	Transformational leadership is an individual's ability to inspire employees, accommodate their interests and in such a way have a strong, fundamental influence on the hearts of other employees. (Ramadhani & Indawati, 2021)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Charismatic Inspiring Motivation Intellectual Stimulation Individual Considerations
Employee Engagement (X2)	Employee engagement is an individual's involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm for the work they do, which reflects the extent to which employees feel motivated, committed, and emotionally connected to the organization. (Simanjuntak & Sitio 2021)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Vigor Dedication Absorption
Organzational Citizenship Behaviour (Z)	Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is voluntary behavior shown by employees in helping coworkers and supporting a positive work environment without any formal demands from the company. (Ananda Muhamad Tri Utama 2022)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Altruism Conscientiousness Sprotmanship Courtesy Civic Virtue
Employee Performance (Y)	Employee performance is the result or level of success of a person in carrying out their duties and responsibilities during a certain period, which is evaluated based on various indicators, such as work standards, targets, goals, or criteria that have been previously determined and agreed upon. (Ridwan et al., 2020)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Work Quality Work Quantity Creative & Innovative Discipline

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Descriptive Analysis Respondents

Identity Responsdence	Category	Frequenct	Percentage
Gender	Male	41	53.95%
	Female	34	46.05%
Age	<30 years	7	9.20%
	31-40 years	24	31.60%
	41-50 years	28	36.80%
	>50 years	17	22.40%
Last Educatin	Junior High School	2	2.63%
	Senior High School	11	14.47%
	Diploma	3	3.95%
	S1	44	57.89%
	S2	16	21.05%

Work Division	Subsection (General Administration Assistant)	12	15.79%
	PBJ Functional (Goods/Services Procurement Section)	12	15.79%
	General Executor	11	14.47%
	Goods/Services Procurement Section (Economic & Development Assistant)	8	10.53%
	Head of Section (General Administration Assistant)	8	10.53%
	Organizational / Legal / Government Section	7	9.21%
	General Affairs Staff	7	9.21%
	Personnel Section	6	7.89%
	Operational Executor	5	6.58%
Year Service	≤5 Years	25	32.89%
	6-10 Years	9	11.84%
	11-20 Years	19	25.00%
	>20 Years	23	30.26%

Based on the table, the total respondents in this study were 76 people with 41 male respondents (53.95%) and 35 female respondents (46.05%). Meanwhile, based on age, the majority of respondents were between 41-50 years old with a percentage of 36.80% and the rest were divided into 30-40 years old and <50 years old. Based on their educational level, the majority of respondents had a Bachelor's (S1) educational background of 44 people or 57.89%, followed by Master's (S2) of 16 people (21.05%). Other respondents came from high school (14.47%), diploma (3.95%), and junior high school (2.63%) levels. Based on organizational structure, respondents came from various work units, with the largest number coming from the Subsection (General Administration Assistant) and PBJ Functional (Goods/Services Procurement Section) with 12 people each, or 15.79%. Followed by General Executor (14.47%), Goods/Services Procurement Section (Economic and Development Assistant) and Head of Section (General Administration Assistant) with 10.53% each. Other respondents were spread across the Organization, Legal, Government, General Affairs, Personnel, and Operational Executor sections. Respondent characteristics based on length of service: The majority of respondents in this study had a service period of less than or equal to 5 years, namely 25 people (32.89%), followed by the group with a service period of more than 20 years, namely 23 people (30.26%). Meanwhile, respondents with a service period of between 6 and 10 years were the smallest group, namely only 9 people or 11.84%.

Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	Items	Outer loading	AVE	Information
Employee Performance	Work Behavior	WB1	0.860	0.699	Valid
		WB2	0.826		Valid
		WB3	0.750		Valid
		WB4	0.762		Valid
		WB5	0.836		Valid
		WB6	0.841		Valid
		WB7	0.744		Valid
		WB8	0.881		Valid
		WB9	0.885		Valid
		WB10	0.879		Valid
		WB11	0.858		Valid
		WB12	0.854		Valid
	WB13	0.874	Valid		
	EPT1	0.902	0.743	Valid	

	Employee Performance Targets	EPT 2	0.869		Valid
		EPT3	0.846		Valid
		EPT4	0.908		Valid
		EPT5	0.847		Valid
		EPT6	0.796		Valid
Engagement Employee	Vigor	EE1	0.818	0.643	Valid
		EE2	0.823		Valid
		EE3	0.864		Valid
		EE4	0.711		Valid
		EE5	0.718		Valid
		EE6	0.861		Valid
	Dedication	EE7	0.815	0.776	Valid
		EE8	0.943		Valid
	Absorption	EE9	0.791	0.706	Valid
		EE10	0.855		Valid
		EE11	0.873		Valid
Transformation Leadership	Individualized Consideration	TL1	0.814	0.717	Valid
		TL2	0.843		Valid
		TL3	0.887		Valid
		TL4	0.841		Valid
	Intellectual Stimulation	TL5	0.735	0.553	Valid
		TL6	0.703		Valid
		TL7	0.775		Valid
		TL8	0.768		Valid
		TL9	0.735		Valid
	Inspirational Motivation	TL10	0.924	0.851	Valid
		TL11	0.921		Valid
	Idealized Influence	TL12	0.804	0.73	Valid
		TL13	0.877		Valid
		TL14	0.914		Valid
		TL15	0.891		Valid
		TL16	0.803		Valid
		TL17	0.829		Valid
OCB	Altruism	OCB1	0.804	0.635	Valid
		OCB2	0.726		Valid
		OCB3	0.796		Valid
		OCB4	0.848		Valid
		OCB5	0.806		Valid
	Conscientiousness	OCB6	0.730	0.593	Valid
		OCB7	0.739		Valid
		OCB8	0.845		Valid
		OCB9	0.761		Valid
	Sportmanship	OCB10	0.892	0.816	Valid
		OCB11	0.904		Valid
		OCB12	0.892		Valid

	Courtesy	OCB13	0.925		Valid
		OCB14	0.860	0.688	Valid
		OCB15	0.913		Valid
		OCB16	0.906		Valid
		OCB17	0.782		Valid
	Civic Virtue	OCB18	0.838	0.751	Valid
		OCB19	0.885		Valid
		OCB20	0.760		Valid

Source: Data diolah (2025)

Based on the results of the convergent validity test for the first-order constructs, all variables in this study demonstrated an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value above 0.5 and an indicator outer loading value above 0.7, indicating that all indicators were considered valid and adequately represented their constructs.

Reliability Test

Variabele	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
PK	0.964	0.968	Reliabel
SKP	0.931	0.945	Reliabel
Vigor	0.887	0.915	Reliabel
Dedication	0.730	0.874	Reliabel
Absorption	0.792	0.878	Reliabel
Individualized Consideration	0.868	0.910	Reliabel
Intellectual Stimulation	0.800	0.861	Reliabel
Inspirational Motivation	0.825	0.920	Reliabel
Idealized Influence	0.925	0.942	Reliabel
Altruism	0.856	0.897	Reliabel
Conscientiousness	0.770	0.853	Reliabel
Sportmanship	0.925	0.947	Reliabel
Courtesy	0.772	0.868	Reliabel
Civic Virtue	0.889	0.923	Reliabel

Source: Data Primer diolah (2025)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values in this study are greater than 0.7. These results indicate that each variable has met the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha requirements, thus concluding that all variables are worthy of further analysis to evaluate the inner model.

Second Order Construct Signification Test

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Vigor → Engagement Employee	0.676	14.297	0.000
Dedication → Engagement Employee	0.232	5.435	0.000
Absorption → Engagement Employee	0.264	7.224	0.000
Altruism → OCB	0.276	13.125	0.000
Civic Virtue → OCB	0.286	12.154	0.000
Conscientiousness → OCB	0.191	10.569	0.000
Courtesy → OCB	0.152	8.485	0.000
Sportmanship → OCB	0.264	11.609	0.000
Individualized Consideration → Leadership Transformation	0.346	6.945	0.000
Idealized Influence → Leadership Transformation	0.467	8.760	0.000
Inspirational Motivation → Leadership Transformation	0.161	5.115	0.000
Intellectual Stimulation → Leadership Transformation	0.294	7.436	0.000
Work Behavior → Employee Performance	0.800	14.057	0.000
Employee Performance Targets → Employee Performance	0.388	7.394	0.000

Source: Data Primer diolah (2025)

The table above shows that all dimensions forming the second-order construct in this study have t-statistics greater than 1.96 and p-values <0.05. This indicates that each dimension makes a significant contribution to its parent construct. Therefore, all dimensions can be declared statistically valid and worthy of being retained in the higher-order construct model used in this study. These results support the structural validity of the model at the second-order level.

Collinearity Evaluation Test

Indicator	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)
Absorption	1.977
Altruism	2.439
Civic Virtue	3.579
Conscientiousness	3.589
Courtesy	3.063
Dedication	1.335
Idealized Influence	4.581
Individualized Consideration	2.132

Inspirational Motivation	6.109
Intellectual Stimulation	4.049
Work Behavior	1.090
Employee Performance Targets	1.090
Sportmanship	3.906
Vigor	1.924

Source: Data Primer diolah (2025)

The table above shows that the VIF values for the second-order constructs in this study were mostly below the threshold (VIF <5). However, one construct, Inspirational Motivation, showed a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value of 6.109, which is still within acceptable tolerance limits in the context of the reflective second-order model.

Coefficient of Determination Test

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Performance	0.309	0.281
OCB	0.882	0.878

Source: Data Primer Diolah (2025)

Based on the table above, the analysis results show that the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) construct has an R Square value of 0.882 and an Adjusted R Square of 0.878. This means that 88.2% of the variation in OCB can be explained by the independent variables in the model, and after adjusting for the number of predictors, the model is still able to explain 87.8% of the total variation.

Direct Hypothesis Testing

Hipotesis	Original Sample (O)	95% Interval Kepercayaan Path Coefficient		T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P-Values	Keterangan
		Batas bawah	Batas Atas			
H1. TL → EP	0.087	-0.492	0.813	0.289	0.773	Rejected
H2. EE → EP	0.436	0.173	0.676	3.149	0.002	Accepted
H3. TL → OCB	0.768	0.620	0.886	11.501	0.000	Accepted
H4. EE → OCB	0.239	0.072	0.389	3.018	0.003	Accepted
H5. OCB → EP	0.073	-0.724	0.701	0.208	0,836	Rejected

Source: Data Primer Diolah (2025);

TL=Transformational Leadership; EP= Employee Performance; EE= Employee Engagement, OCB=Organization Citizenship Behavior

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance

Transformational Leadership (TL) does not significantly influence Employee Performance (EP). This is indicated by a p-value of 0.773 > 0.05, thus rejecting H1. The coefficient of influence of KT on KP is 0.087, with a T-statistic of 0.289, which is also below the critical value. This means that although there is a positive relationship, the influence of transformational leadership is not strong enough to directly influence employee performance improvement.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on Employee Performance

Employee Engagement (EE) significantly influences Employee Performance (EP). This is evidenced by a p-value of 0.002 < 0.05 and a T-statistic of 3.149, thus H2 is accepted. The coefficient of influence of EE on KP is 0.436, indicating a positive relationship. This means that the higher the level of employee engagement in an organization, the higher the employee performance tends to be.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on OCB

Transformational Leadership (TL) has a significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). This is indicated by a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a T-statistic of 11.501, thus H3 is accepted. The coefficient of TL's influence on OCB is 0.768, indicating a strong positive relationship. This means that the better the transformational leadership implemented, the higher the tendency of employees to demonstrate positive behaviors such as helping coworkers, being loyal to the organization, and taking initiative beyond their formal duties.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on OCB

Employee Engagement (EE) has a significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). A p-value of 0.003 < 0.05 and a T-statistic of 3.018 indicate that H4 is accepted. The coefficient of EE's influence on OCB of 0.239 indicates a positive relationship. This means that the higher the employee's involvement in their work—whether cognitively, emotionally, or physically—the greater their tendency to exhibit positive behaviors outside of formal duties, such as helping coworkers, maintaining a harmonious work environment, and demonstrating loyalty and concern for the organization.

The Influence of OCB on Employee Performance

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) does not significantly influence Employee Performance (CP). This is evident from the p-value of 0.836 > 0.05 and the T-statistic of 0.208, thus rejecting H5. The coefficient of OCB's influence on KP of 0.073 indicates a positive but very weak and statistically insignificant relationship. This means that although employees demonstrate voluntary behaviors that support the organization, such as helping coworkers or being cooperative, these contributions are not strong enough to have a direct impact on measurable improvements in employee performance.

Indirect Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	95% Interval Kepercayaan Path Coefficient		T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P-Values	Information
		Batas bawah	Batas Atas			
H6. TL → OCB → EP	0.056	-0.638	0,543	0.201	0.841	Rejected
H7. EE → OCB → EP	0.017	-0.113	0,205	0.205	0.837	Rejected

Source: Data Primer Diolah (2025); TL=Transformational Leadership; EP= Employee Performance; OCB=Organization Citizenship Behavior

The table above shows that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) does not act as a significant mediator in either the relationship between Transformational Leadership (H6) or Employee Engagement (EE) on Employee Performance (H7). This is indicated by the p-value of each hypothesis above the threshold (>0.05), which is 0.841 for H6 and 0.837 for H7. Although it shows a positive relationship (H6=0.065; H7=0.017), it is not statistically significant. This finding indicates that OCB has not been able to bridge the influence of Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement effectively on improving employee performance.

CONSLUSION

Based on the results of the research and analysis that has been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. The first hypothesis is rejected, namely that transformational leadership does not significantly influence employee performance. This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of 0.289 < 1.96 and a P-value of 0.773 > 0.05.

2. The second hypothesis is accepted, namely that employee engagement has a significant effect on employee performance. This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of $3.149 > 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.002 < 0.05$.
3. The third hypothesis is accepted, namely that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of $11.501 > 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$.
4. The fourth hypothesis is accepted, namely that employee engagement has a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of $3.018 > 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.003 < 0.05$.
5. The fifth hypothesis is rejected, namely that organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) does not significantly influence employee performance. This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of $0.208 < 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.536 > 0.05$.
6. The sixth hypothesis is rejected, namely that organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) cannot mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. This is proven through hypothesis testing, where the T-statistic value is $0.201 < 1.96$ and the P-value is $0.841 > 0.05$.
7. The seventh hypothesis is rejected, namely that organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) cannot mediate the relationship between employee engagement and employee performance. This is proven through a hypothesis test with a T-statistic of $0.205 < 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.837 > 0.05$.

REFERENCES

1. Alshaabani, A., Naz, F., Magda, R., & Rudnák, I. (2021). Impact of perceived organizational support on ocb in the time of covid-19 pandemic in hungary: Employee engagement and affective commitment as mediators. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147800>
2. ANANDA MUHAMAD TRI UTAMA. (2022). *Determinasi Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) dan Loyalitas Karyawan: Analisis Pengetahuan, Komitmen Organisasi dan Motivasi Kerja (Studi Literature Review)*. 9(4), 356–363.
3. Atthohiri, N. A., & Wijayati, D. T. (2021). Pengaruh Employee Engagement terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dengan Work Life Balance sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 9(3), 1092–1100. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jim.v9n3.p1092-1100>
4. Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1994). Re-examining the components of transformational and transactional leadership using the multifactor leadership questionnaire. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 72(4), 441–462. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317999166789>
5. Awalia, F. Y., & Yanuar, Y. (2024). the Influence of Employee Engagement and Organizational Support on Employee Performance Mediated By Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *International Journal of Application on Economics and Business*, 2(2), 3308–3317. <https://doi.org/10.24912/ijaeb.v2i2.3308-3317>
6. Fadilah, M. A., & Wilian, R. (2023). *Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Pt . Enseval Putera Megatrading , Tbk Cabang Jambi*. 11(1), 25–37.
7. Istanti, E., Negoro, B. K. N., & Daengs, A. (2021). the Effect of Job Stress and Financial Compensation Toward. *Media Mahardhika*, 19(3), 560–570.
8. Kementerian PANRB RI. (2022). Peraturan Menteri PANRB Nomor 6 Tahun 2022 tentang Pengelolaan Kinerja Aparatur Sipil Negara. *Berita Negara Republik Indonesia*, 155, 1–240.
9. Kurniawati, N. I., & Raharja, E. (2023). The Influence of Employee Engagement on Organizational Performance: A Systematic Review. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 20, 203–213. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2023.20.20>
10. Mahmudi, B., & Farida Elmi. (2020). Effect of Leader Member Exchange, Organizational Culture and Employee Engagement on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Case Study Gen Y in Perum Lppnpi). *Dinasti International Journal of Economics, Finance & Accounting*, 1(1), 71–82. <https://doi.org/10.38035/dijefa.v1i1.224>
11. Nemr, M. A. A., & liu, Y. (2021). The impact of ethical leadership on organizational citizenship behaviors: Moderating role of organizational cynicism. *Cogent Business and Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1865860>
12. Organ, D. W. (1995). A meta-analytic review of attitudinal and dispositional predictors of organizational citizenship. In *Personel Psychology* (Vol. 48, Issue 4, pp. 775–802).

13. Ramadhani, M. A., & Indawati, N. (2021). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan melalui Otonomi Kerja. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 9(3), 1101–1112. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jim.v9n3.p1101-1112>
14. Ridwan, M., Mulyani, S. R., & Ali, H. (2020). Improving employee performance through perceived organizational support, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(12), 839–849. <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.5.123>
15. Robbins, S. P. (2003). *Perilaku organisasi*. PT. Indeks Kelompok Gramedia.
16. Saputro, R. (2021). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan OCB Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Motivasi. *Jurnal EMBA*, 9(2), 1103–1119.
17. Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. (2016). UWES Utrecht work engagement scale preliminary manual. *Occupational Health Psychology Unit, Utrecht University*, 1, 4–58.
18. Shams, M. S., Niazi, M. M., & Asim, F. (2020). The Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support, Employee Engagement, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Application of PLS-SEM Approach. *Kardan Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.31841/kjems.2021.37>
19. Simanjuntak, T., & Sitio, V. S. S. (2021). Pengaruh Knowledge Sharing dan Employee Engagement Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Narma Toserba, Narogong Bogor. *Jurnal Inovatif Mahasiswa Manajemen*, 2(1), 42–54.
20. Sugiharjo, R. J. (2020). Influence of Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) on Employee Performance. *Journal of Resources Development and Management*, 42–50. <https://doi.org/10.7176/jrdm/62-06>
21. Supriyanto, A. S., Ekowati, V. M., Pujiyanto, Z. T., & Masyhuri. (2021). Employee Engagement: A Quantitative Review and Its Relationship with Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Social Science (ICONETOS 2020)*, 529(Iconetos 2020), 268–273. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210421.038>
22. Wiguna, P. K. S., Martini, N. N. P., Qomariah, N., Satoto, E. B., & Thamrin, M. (2022). The Role of Leadership, Employee Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance Improvement. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 6, 122–131.
23. Zalianty, R., & Rojuaniah. (2023). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Prestasi Kerja dan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Melalui Corporate Social Responsibility. *ADI Bisnis Digital Interdisiplin Jurnal*, 4(1), 118–125. <https://doi.org/10.34306/abdi.v4i1.898>

Cite this Article: Darmaeti, H., Siswanti, Y., Ambarwati, S.D.A. (2025). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance Mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) on ASN Employees at the Gunungkidul Regional Secretariat Office. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(9), pp. 4441-4453. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i9-05>